

Comparison of the quality of single-crystal diamonds grown on two types of seed substrates by MPCVD

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Abstract: Microwave plasma chemical vapor deposition (MPCVD) was used to grow single-crystal diamonds on two types of single-crystal diamond seed substrates prepared by high-pressure, high-temperature (HPHT) and chemical vapor deposition (CVD) methods. The quality of diamonds grown on the different seed substrates was compared. Fluorescence characteristics showed that the sectors of the HPHT seed substrates were obviously partitioned. Raman and absorption spectra showed that the CVD seed substrate produced higher-quality crystals with fewer nitrogen impurities. X-ray topography showed that the HPHT seed substrate had obvious growth sector boundaries, inclusions, dislocations, and stacking faults. The polarization characteristics of HPHT seed substrate were obvious, and the stress distribution was not uniform. When etching HPHT and CVD seed substrates using the same parameters, the etching morphology and extent of different growth sectors of the two substrates differed. Although extended defects were inevitably formed at the interface and propagated in the CVD layer, the dislocation density of a 1 mm-thick CVD layer grown on a CVD seed substrate was only half that of a 1 mm-thick CVD layer grown on an HPHT seed substrate. Therefore, the use of CVD seed substrate enabled the growth of a relatively higher-quality CVD single-crystal diamond.

Keywords: A3. MPCVD, A2. Diamond growth, A1. Dislocations, A1. Defects, A1. X-ray topography.

1. Introduction

Diamonds have extremely high hardness and therefore are commonly used as cutting tools [1]. In addition, diamonds have excellent physical and electrical properties and are widely used in industrial and scientific applications. They are expected to become ideal materials for optical and next-generation electronic devices, such as monochromators for synchrotron X-ray beams, optics, high-power electronics, quantum computing devices, highly sensitive detectors, and biological and chemical sensors [2-8].

Microwave plasma chemical vapor deposition (MPCVD) has become the most important method for synthesizing high-purity single-crystal diamonds on a millimeter scale [9,10]. However, the extended defects produced by this method remain a major problem [11]. In diamonds created through chemical vapor deposition (CVD), there are edge or 45 ° mixed dislocations along the direction of growth [12,13] that can easily lead to impurities and vacancies and affect the optical and electronic properties of the diamonds. Therefore, suppression of defects in diamonds is needed to make them useful for the next generation of electronic devices [14,15].

Current research on the growth of CVD diamonds mainly focuses on the growth size of CVD

single-crystal diamonds [16], nitrogen doping and its influence on the growth rate of single-crystal diamonds [17], and ways to control defects in single-crystal diamonds [18]. Crystal defects can be suppressed by optimizing the growth process, but the quality of homoepitaxial CVD diamonds depends not only on the parameters of the growth process but also on the quality of the seed substrate [19]. High-pressure, high-temperature (HPHT) type I b seed substrate is low-cost and widely used, so it is sometimes unavoidable to use it for growing single-crystal diamonds. However, it contains extended defects such as impurities, dislocations, and growth sectors [20]. Dislocations in the seed substrate can propagate into the CVD layer, and other types of defects can also have an effect on growth [21]. Studying the influence of different types and qualities of seed substrates on the epitaxial growth of a CVD layer can help achieve high-quality CVD single-crystal diamonds.

2. Experimental details

A home-made 2.45-GHz microwave plasma reactor [22] was used for MPCVD. Commercial HPHT type I b and optical grade CVD type IIa seed substrates were used in the experiment. Their top and lateral sides {100} were $4 \times 4 \times 1$ mm³. H₂ and O₂ plasma etching was performed at 900 °C for 30 min to remove impurities on the seed surface and polishing-induced damage. High-purity hydrogen (6N) and methane (6N) gases were used as the process gas. No nitrogen was intentionally added in the gas phase, however, nitrogen was present at least as background impurities. After the optimization process, the HPHT and CVD seed substrates were grown under optimized growth conditions. A growth power of 2.6–2.9 kW, the reactor was maintained at a pressure of 25–27 kPa and a concentration of 5% CH₄ diluted in H₂. After 50 h of growth, a 1 mm-thick CVD layer was obtained. The crystal grew both vertically and horizontally, with a smooth top surface and no polycrystalline rim.

DiamondView™ equipment was used to observe the fluorescence and growth structure of the seed substrate under UV light at a wavelength of around 230 nm. A Keyence VHX-6000 3D Digital Microscope was used to observe the etched pits and surface morphologies of the seed substrates after growth. The HPHT and CVD seed substrates were tested at room temperature using a Renishaw in a Via-Reflex Raman spectrometer with 532-nm and 633-nm lasers (laser beam spot-size was about 1 μm). The random error of measuring the full width at half-maximum (FWHM) of the diamond peak (with a wavenumber of about 1332 cm⁻¹), as well as its position in the spectrum amounted to not more than 0.1 cm⁻¹. In order to further analyze the quality of crystals and impurity concentration of the seed substrates, the absorption spectra of HPHT and CVD seed substrates were tested using Excalibur 3100 Fourier-transformation infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and a Cary 5000 ultraviolet and visible light (UV-Vis) spectrometer. Birefringence photographs of the HPHT and CVD seed substrates were measured with an Olympus BX51 microscope. The rocking curves of the two types of seed substrates and CVD layers grown on each were measured by a Bruker D8 DISCOVER X-ray high-resolution diffractometer using a monochromized Cu-Kα₁ X-ray source with a Ge (220) four-crystal monochromator. X-ray topography is a powerful tool for studying extended defects such as dislocations and stacking faults [23,24]. X-ray topography was performed on two types of seed substrates and the samples grown on each.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Impurity analysis of HPHT and CVD seed substrates

Fig. 1 shows optical and fluorescence images of the HPHT and CVD seed substrates. Fig. 1 (a) and (b) are optical images of the HPHT and CVD seed substrates, respectively, while Fig. 1 (c) and (d) are fluorescence images of the HPHT and CVD seed substrates, respectively. The HPHT seed substrate has a typical deep yellow color (Fig. 1 (a)). The HPHT seed substrate, on the other hand, has yellow-green fluorescence, as revealed by DiamondView™, and different growth sectors display different colors (Fig. 1 (c)). The white dotted area is the (100) growth sector, which features yellow-green fluorescence, and the yellow and red dotted areas represent the (110) and (113) growth sectors, respectively. The color emitted by diamonds under DiamondView™ depends on the type and amount of impurities contained in the diamond [25]. The HPHT seed substrate features green fluorescence due to a nitrogen-vacancy-nitrogen (H3) defect. The nitrogen content of the (100) growth sector is higher than that of the (113) and (110) growth sectors [20]. Due to different growth sectors' abilities to adsorb nitrogen, the color of fluorescence will appear to be zoned. The CVD seed substrate shows no color (Fig. 1 (b)) but exhibits orange-red fluorescence (Fig. 1 (d)) under DiamondView™, which is a typical luminescent feature of CVD diamonds caused by nitrogen-vacancy (NV) defects [26]. The fluorescence color of the CVD seed substrate is uniform, indicating that the impurity content is evenly distributed.

Fig. 1. (a) and (b) are optical images of HPHT and CVD seed substrates, respectively, and (c) and (d) are fluorescence images of HPHT and CVD seed substrates, respectively. (c) The white dotted area is the (100) growth sector, the yellow dotted area is the (110) growth sector, and the red dotted area is the (113) growth sector.

Fig. 2 (a) shows that the CVD seed substrate has a narrow diamond Raman peak and a full width at half maximum (FWHM) of 2.8 cm^{-1} . The upper inset shows nitrogen-vacancy defects (NV centers). The HPHT seed substrate has no NV centers, but its FWHM is 3.1 cm^{-1} .

A broad absorption band with maximum intensity at a wavelength of 270 nm is produced by

electronic transitions from the valence band to the nitrogen C defects. The 270-nm band can be seen in diamonds with concentrations of C defects as low as 0.01 ppm, which is significantly below the detection limit of FTIR absorption spectroscopy [27]. The inset of Fig. 2 (b) shows the curve after the third-order polynomial fit in the blue dotted line of the absorption spectrum of the CVD seed substrate. After fitting [28], the absorption coefficient at 270 nm can be obtained. The nitrogen content of the CVD seed substrate was found to be about 0.3 ppm.

The C-center is one of the most common FTIR optical centers in diamonds. It has a sharp peak at a wavenumber of $1,344\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a band with a maximum at a wavenumber of $1,130\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The FTIR spectra of the deep yellow HPHT seed substrate and the colorless CVD seed substrate are shown in Fig. 2 (c). Both types of seed substrates have infrared absorption peaks from $1,500\text{--}2,800\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which is the intrinsic absorption peak of diamond. The inset is a magnified view of the green dotted area in Figure 2 (c), showing two characteristic peaks of the C-center of the HPHT seed substrate. The C-center concentration can be estimated by measuring absorption intensities at a wavenumber of $1,130\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a sharp peak at a wavenumber of $1,344\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The nitrogen content (N_c) of the HPHT seed substrate is about 59 ppm, which was calculated by the formula [27]: $N_c(\text{ppm})=(25\pm 2)\mu_{1130}$, where μ is the absorption coefficient with unit of cm^{-1} .

Fig. 2. (a) Raman spectra of the HPHT and CVD seed substrates. The excitation wavelength is 633 nm and the diamond Raman peak was vertically shifted for clarity. The spectra shows the diamond Raman peaks and their FWHM (w). The inset shows the diamond Raman peaks of the seed substrates at an excitation wavelength of 532 nm. NV is the emission peak of nitrogen-vacancy defects. (b) UV-Vis absorption spectra of the HPHT and CVD seed substrates. The inset is the curve after the third-order polynomial fit in the blue dotted line of the absorption spectrum of the CVD seed substrate. (c) FTIR spectra of the HPHT and CVD seed substrates. The

inset is a magnified view of the green dotted area. The sharp peak at a wavenumber of $1,344\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and band with a maximum at a wavenumber of $1,130\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are dominant infrared absorption features of type Ib diamonds.

3.2 Extended defect analysis of the HPHT and CVD seed substrates

Fig. 3 shows X-ray topography images of HPHT and CVD seed substrates. Growth sector boundaries (I) and a strain field around a microscopic inclusion (IV) can be distinguished in Fig. 3 (a), indicating a large amount of strain. Other defects, such as dislocations (II), and stacking faults (III), are also visible and create local stresses in crystal. The dislocations are observed as individual black lines radiating mainly from the center of the sample. Stacking faults are observed, as trapezoidal-shaped areas, at the periphery of HPHT seed substrate. Fig. 3 (b) shows an X-ray topography image of the CVD seed substrate, revealing only one extended defect: dislocations.

Fig. 3. X-ray topography images of HPHT and CVD seed substrates. (a) X-ray topography image of HPHT seed substrates. Main defects such as growth sector boundaries (I), dislocations (II), stacking faults (III), and strain field of inclusion (IV) are visible. (b) X-ray topography image of CVD seed substrate. There is only one extended defect: dislocations.

Figs. 4 (a) and (b) show the birefringence patterns of seed substrates under cross-polarizers, which are related to the local stress distribution of dislocations [29,30]. The content of nitrogen impurities differs in different growth sectors of the HPHT seed substrate. The atomic radius of nitrogen is larger than that of carbon atom, so nitrogen atoms will cause lattice expansion pressure. When the impurities are evenly distributed, the lattice deformation is uniform and does not show obvious abnormal birefringence. However, often, the impurity content of each growth sector is different and the nitrogen impurities in the same growth sector are uneven, resulting in different degrees of lattice strain. Moreover, dislocations are more likely to appear on the $\{111\}$ surface

with higher atomic surface density, leading to different stress states in different growth sectors and thus to abnormal birefringence.

Fig. 4. Birefringence patterns of seed substrates under cross-polarizers. (a) HPHT seed substrate. (b) CVD seed substrate.

Fig. 5 (a) shows the whole image of the HPHT seed substrate after plasma etching. The surface morphology varies after plasma etching in each growth sector. The magnified image shows that the etch pit density of the (100) growth sector is less than that of the (113) and (110) growth sectors and that etch pits in the (110) growth sector are obviously larger than in the other two growth sectors, and the etching shows anisotropy. Fig. 5 (b) shows that the surface morphology of the CVD seed substrate is uniform after plasma etching. And the most etch pits have a point bottom shape, which are related to threading dislocations. The flat bottom etch pits are related to polishing induced damage that was not fully removed.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5. Microscope images of HPHT and CVD seed substrates after plasma etching. (a) The whole image of the HPHT seed substrate is on the left, and the magnified image is on the right. The morphology of the HPHT seed substrate differs in different growth sectors after plasma etching. (b) Microscope image of CVD seed substrate after etching. The whole image on the left shows that the surface morphology of CVD seed substrate is uniform after plasma etching. The magnified image shows that most of the etch pits are point bottom that are indicated by red arrows, and flat bottom etch pits are indicated by blue arrows.

Nitrogen impurities can alter the mechanical properties of diamond [31], which affect the quality of the polished diamond surface. The extent of etching and morphology of HPHT and CVD seed substrates differ due to different nitrogen contents, and stress differs in different areas of the HPHT seed substrate. Therefore, the amount removed by etching differs in different positions, resulting in increased surface roughness and inducing more dislocations in the CVD layer.

3.3 Quality analysis of the CVD layers

The thickness of the CVD layer increased by nearly 1 mm after growth for 50 h on a CVD seed substrate. The CVD layer became thicker and the top surface area increased. As shown in Figs. 6 (a) and (b), the CVD layer grows both vertically and horizontally and the top surface is smooth with no polycrystalline rim. Fig. 6 (c) shows the surface morphology of the sample, which features clear step-flow growth with a step width of about 5 µm.

Fig. 6. (a, b) The as-grown CVD seed substrate after growth for 50 h. The CVD layer grows both vertically and horizontally, and the top surface is smooth with no polycrystalline rim. (c) The surface morphology of the sample, which shows clear step-flow growth.

Figs. 7 (a) and (b) show X-ray topography images of as-grown HPHT seed substrate. X-ray topography images of as-grown CVD seed substrate in Figs. 7 (c) and (d). Figs. 7 (a) and (c) show that dislocations in the seed substrate extend into the CVD layer. Some dislocations are formed at the interface between the substrate and CVD layer, which is caused by defects at the interface. Stacking faults are not transferred to the CVD layer, but they can act as sources of dislocation. They tend to etch preferentially at the start of the CVD process, leaving grooves that act as sources of many closely spaced dislocations [32].

The HPHT seed substrate contains some nitrogen impurities, which increases the lattice parameter of the crystal. When a higher-purity CVD layer grows on such substrate, tension will form at the interface, increasing the likelihood of nucleation of dislocations. X-ray topography shows that dislocations form at the interface and propagate along the growth direction of the CVD layer (Fig. 7 (a)). When a CVD seed substrate with low nitrogen content is used, it is possible to achieve better matching and reduce dislocations formed at the interface shown in Fig. 7 (c).

Fig. 7. (a, b) X-ray topography images of as-grown HPHT seed substrate. (c, d) X-ray topography images of as-grown CVD seed substrate.

The X-ray rocking curve is very sensitive to dislocations and other defects in the crystal, and the quality of the crystal can be judged according to the FWHM of rocking curve [23]. When the dislocation density is high (10^4 – 10^7 cm^{-2}), the dislocation density (N_d) of the sample can be calculated from the FWHM of rocking curve, which was calculated by the formula [33]: $N_d = (\Delta\theta_{1/2})^2 / 9b^2$, where $\Delta\theta_{1/2}$ and b are the real FWHM of the double crystal diffraction of a specimen crystal and Burgers vector length, respectively. And $\Delta\theta_{1/2} = (\beta^2 - \Delta\theta_{1/2}'^2)^{1/2}$, where β and $\Delta\theta_{1/2}'$ are the measurement FWHM of the double crystal diffraction of a specimen crystal and the real FWHM of the first crystal, respectively. Ge (220) four crystal monochromator cause the width of the rocking curve is 12 rad·s. Fig. 8 shows the rocking curves and the FWHM of the HPHT and CVD seed substrates as well as CVD layer 1 and CVD layer 2, which were grown on

the HPHT and CVD seed substrates, respectively. The FWHM of both seed substrates is 0.01° , and the FWHMs of the corresponding CVD layers are 0.03° and 0.02° , respectively. The dislocation density of both seed substrates is $4.6 \times 10^6 \text{ cm}^{-2}$, and the dislocation densities of the corresponding CVD layers are $4.7 \times 10^7 \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (CVD layer 1) and $2.0 \times 10^7 \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (CVD layer 2). The dislocation density of the CVD layer grown on the CVD seed substrate is half that of the CVD layer grown on the HPHT seed substrate. Dislocations were then revealed by etching. In order to avoid polishing-induced surface damage, we etched directly the dislocations emerging at the step-flow surface by a plasma treatment in our CVD reactor. Fig. 9 shows the etched surfaces of the CVD layer1 and CVD layer2, and the etch-pits are almost exclusively of the point-bottom type. CVD layer 1 exhibits dislocation densities at least 2 times that of CVD layer 2. Due to the high dislocation density of CVD layer 1, the crystal perfection is generally low, and individual dislocations are not resolved in the X-ray topography image. A similar mosaic structure [34] appears in the crystal shown in Fig. 7 (b). It is also evident from the topography that a large number of dislocations nucleate at the interface.

Fig. 8. The rocking curves and the FWHM (w) of the HPHT and CVD seed substrates as well as CVD layers 1 and 2.

Fig. 9. The etched surfaces of the CVD layer1 (a) and CVD layer2 (b), and the etch-pits indicated by red arrows are almost exclusively of the point-bottom type.

4. Conclusion

A comprehensive study of HPHT type I b and CVD type II a seed substrates has been conducted. Although there are some impurities and defects in the CVD seed substrate, it still produces higher-quality crystals than the HPHT seed substrate with many types of extended defects.

The quality of CVD layers grown on the HPHT and CVD seed substrates was compared. The dislocation density of the CVD layer grown on the CVD seed substrate was much lower than that of the CVD layer grown on the HPHT seed substrate. The crystal quality of the homoepitaxial CVD layer is related not only to the dislocation of the seed substrate but also to other types of defects, such as impurities in the seed substrate and growth sectors. Therefore, prior to the growth of a high-quality single-crystal diamond, a CVD seed substrate with a low impurity content and few expansion defects should be selected. This study emphasizes the importance of selecting a high-quality substrate for growth of single-crystal diamonds.

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